

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPENSATIONS FOR WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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ABSTRACT: This article talks about the practical work being done for the education of children with disabilities, inclusive education and the adopted law on this education, as well as the current problems and shortcomings in this regard. .

Key words: Pedagogical technologies, special education, lesson, pedagogue, efficiency, education and training, children with disabilities.

INTRODUCTION

On October 13, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at improving inclusive education in Uzbekistan, forming a system of education for children with special educational needs, training pedagogues, and improving the quality of educational services provided to them. The decision "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" was adopted. With this decision, the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system was adopted in 2020-2025. The "Roadmap" for the implementation of the concept for 2020-2021 was approved.

It is noteworthy that in 2023-2025, the inclusive education system will be introduced in 51 percent of general education schools. 40 percent of children with disabilities are involved in this form of education. Children with disabilities are included in music, painting, visual arts, ceramics, physical education and sports, computers, sewing and other extracurricular clubs. At the same time, teaching methods are improved in inclusive education and the principles of individualization are gradually introduced into the educational process.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The main task of logopedic work in schools for children with disabilities (mental retardation) is the comprehensive development of the personality of the mentally retarded student, as well as measures aimed at correcting, alleviating, and compensating for various defects in mental and physical development that cause this category of children to lag behind socially. - focused on the implementation of activities.

All speech defects of children with disabilities cause difficulties in the process of teaching them, they do not always understand the teacher's explanations, they do not understand the teacher's explanations correctly. However, the experiences of advanced teachers-defectologists have shown that

with the help of a specially organized process of education, it is possible to correct the speech activity of students with mental retardation, that is, to improve their role in the development of the general personality. The first 2 weeks of the academic year are focused on identifying and checking the speech of new students. In this case, the speech therapist examines the student's oral and written speech in 2 stages: At the 1st stage, the speech of the students in the class is checked in general condition and children with speech defects are identified among the students; In the 2nd stage, a student with a speech impairment is identified and diagnosed individually in the conditions of a speech therapy room.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plan of individual training is mainly reflected in the speech card of the speech pathologist. Organization of logopedic examination of the speech process Examination of the speech of first-grade students with disabilities begins with the study of the student during the lesson. Such a frontal (gross) examination not only saves time for the speech therapist, but it allows to observe the natural state of the students' speech activity, clearly expresses the students' response and the state of oral speech. At the same time, the speech therapist will have the opportunity to get acquainted with the personal characteristics of the students: work skills, attention, memory, intellectual level. Frontal inspection can be carried out in different ways, as well as in an integrated way. In this case, the speech therapist observes the students' answers in the teacher's office, and then, in turn, the speech therapist conducts a question-and-answer session based on a meaningful picture recommended by him, and asks him to make up a story and speak.

Currently, the special boarding school for the blind in the 12th year education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is training teachers with pedagogical competence to teach visually impaired and blind children. Starting from 2020, by the decree of the President, education in these schools was set to 11 years. Due to the fact that this period is not enough for children with visual impairments to learn full subjects and vital knowledge, to acquire any profession in the future, blind people of Tashkent city No. 77 and Kosonsoy district No. 45 of Namangan region In the appeal made by the teachers and educators of the special boarding school to the Minister of Public Education and the President, the need to return such special schools to the previous 12-year education was shown and asked with important reasons. After that, such schools were returned to the previous 12-year education system.

CONCLUSION

In order to introduce this educational system, it is first necessary to adapt the society, both healthy children in school and children with disabilities. Especially children studying in primary school do not know what disability is and that such children should not be laughed at. Therefore, if during inclusive education they laugh at, make fun of, isolate, and humiliate a peer with a disability, it will definitely have a serious impact on the psyche of a child with a disability. Feeling discriminated against among healthy children causes the child to live under constant mental stress. In special boarding schools, in the process of education and upbringing, children with similar disabilities do not experience excessive mental pressure because their peers are similar to them and suffer from the same disease. They do not feel weak and weak from those around them.

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